

Developing Framework for Adoption of Open Science and Research Data Management for Sustainable Library and Information Science Research and Practice in Nigerian Library Schools

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ABSTRACT

Background: Open science and research data management are critical factors for a sustainable library and information science research and practices.

Method: This study adopted a conceptual approach through literature review to identify the roles of open science and research data management for sustainable library and information science research and practices in Nigerian library schools.

Findings/Results: The study identified a framework for sustainable library and information science research and practice, and its' outcome for library and information science schools. Also, the strategies towards actualization of sustainable library and information science research and practice in Nigerian library schools were enumerated.

Conclusion: The study concludes that sustainable library and information science research through open science and research data management is very significant in the digital age. It further concludes that Nigerian library schools are still struggling with these initiatives due to inadequate skills, technological decay, and poor funding.

Recommendations: Nigerian library schools should integrate open science and research data management into their curricula, implement continuous capacity-building for faculty and students, invest in modern digital infrastructure, and strengthen international partnerships for effective knowledge and resource sharing.

Keywords: Sustainable Library, Information Science, Research and Practice, Open Science, Research Data Management

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable library and information science represents an important and emerging field at the intersection of research and practice. It advances theoretical and empirical inquiry into how LIS contributes to sustainable development in research. In practice, it guides libraries in aligning their policies, services, and infrastructure with sustainability goals to strengthen LIS as a central contributor to building resilient, inclusive, and sustainable knowledge societies. The concept of sustainability in library and information science (LIS) encompasses the ability to maintain and improve library services and resources over time, to ensure that they meet the needs of present and future users (Madu, Odenigbo & Yakubu, 2024). The principles of open science and research data management (OS-RDM) promote transparency at every phase of the research process and highlight the appropriate management of scientific information. Promotion of openness, cooperation, and long-term access to research products are crucial principles for increasing the sustainability of library and information science (LIS) education (Lisée & Robert, 2023; Borghi & Van Gulick, 2022), and these sustainable practices are critical to ensuring the discipline's continued significance and utility in the digital age.

The rapidly changing setting of library and information science (LIS) necessitates a focus on sustainable practices that can adapt to technological advancements and societal needs. In this context, open science and research data management (RDM) have emerged as critical methodologies for promoting transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in academic and professional library and information science settings (Ghannad et al., 2023; Borghi & Van Gulick, 2022). Research data management entails organising, storing, preserving, and sharing data collected during research, and the practices are critical for ensuring the integrity and reproducibility of research findings (Cox & Pinfield, 2013). In LIS education, teaching research data management skills is essential for preparing students to manage data effectively in their future careers (Xu, Zhou, Kogut, & Clough, 2022). Studies have highlighted the growing importance of research data management in LIS curricula and the need for comprehensive training programs in some developing countries, such as Malawi (Chawinga & Zinn, 2020), Tanzania (Mosha & Ngulube, 2022), Malaysia (Amanullah & Abrizah, 2023) and others. However, the acquisition of skills on data organisation, metadata format, and the use of repository systems presents a persistent challenge for library schools in Nigeria (Alex-Nmecha & Onifade, 2023).

The use of open science and research data management has the potential to improve research transparency and accessibility, as well as the prudent administration of data, both of which are essential elements of contemporary LIS education and practice (Fecher & Friesike, 2013; Patel & Thakur, 2020). In emerging nations such as Nigeria, the use of these approaches is especially important because they can help to mitigate disparities in resources and information availability (Ezema, 2013).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Library and Information Science (LIS) education plays a critical role in shaping the future of information management, particularly in Nigeria, where the need for sustainable research and professional practice is growing. Despite the increasing importance of open science and research data management (RDM) in global LIS education, Nigerian library schools have been slow to adopt these practices. This lag presents several challenges which include inadequate preparation of LIS students for the evolving demands of the profession, research outputs from Nigerian institutions lack visibility and impact, and opportunities for collaboration and innovation through open science are being missed.

The absence of a clear framework for integrating open science and research data management into LIS curricula exacerbates these issues, leaving Nigerian library schools behind in the global movement towards sustainable and impactful research practices. Moreover, the lack of designed steps for promoting sustainable LIS research in these institutions further hampers progress. The integration of open science and research data management into LIS education in Nigeria is crucial for developing a workforce capable of implementing sustainable practices. While there is growing awareness of these practices, their integration into curricula remains limited (Isah, Salma & Adekeye, 2021; Alex-Nmecha & Nsirim, 2023). This gap underscores the need for targeted efforts to incorporate Open Science and research data management into LIS programmes, ensuring that future professionals are well-equipped to handle the challenges of modern librarianship. Hence, this research seeks to develop framework for sustainable LIS research and practice through open science and research data management in Nigerian library school and recommend the steps towards sustainable library and information science research and practice in Nigerian library schools.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study adopted content analysis through an in-depth literature review of related articles on sustainable library and information science research and practice with focus on open science and research data management. The search for relevant articles did not take any particular sequence as information were gathered from various information sources on the internet. The result of the review yield the designing of a framework. The framework was designed based on the gap in literature, especially the ones emanating from Nigerian LIS professionals.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sustainable Library and Information Science Practices and Open Science Initiative

Sustainable LIS practices involve the adoption of strategies that ensure long-term viability and relevance of library services. According to Jankowska & Marcum (2010) sustainability in academic libraries includes environmental, economic, and social dimensions, requiring a holistic approach to resource management and service delivery. Libraries must continually evolve to meet changing user expectations and technological advancements (Fourie & Meyer, 2016).

In Nigeria, the implementation of sustainable LIS practices is still in its nascent stages. Several studies have highlighted the challenges faced by Nigerian libraries, including inadequate funding, limited access to digital resources, and a lack of trained personnel (Omekwu, 2006; Ocholla et al., 2012; Saibakumo, 2021). At professional level, Diseiye et al. (2023) uncovered digital literacy for self-sufficiency as the driver of the use of emerging technologies among library professionals. Despite these challenges, there have been efforts to promote sustainable practices through the adoption of Open Science and RDM. For instance, Ezema (2013), Ejikeme and Ezema, (2019) discusses the potential of open access initiatives and intuitional repositories to improve access to information in Nigerian libraries.

As a movement towards more open, transparent, and accessible research practices (Vicente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018), with aim to enhance the reproducibility and dissemination of research findings, thereby increasing their impact and utility (Vicente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018), Open science encompasses various practices, including open access publishing, open data, and collaborative research. In the context of LIS, Open Science is seen as a way to democratize access to information and foster collaborative research efforts (Pampel & Dallmeier-Tiessen, 2013; Fecher & Friesike, 2014), which is crucial for fostering a culture of sharing and collaboration among researchers and practitioners (Nazim & Ali, 2023). It potentials include the visibility and impact of research, which is particularly beneficial for researchers in developing countries (Tennant et al., 2016).

The significance of sustainable library practices and the Open Science Initiative in Nigerian library schools continues to rise due to the alignment with global sustainability ideals and facilitation of improved academic outcomes. These efforts improve inclusiveness, resource management, and advocacy for unrestricted access to information, all of which are critical for the advancement of library schools in Nigeria. Moreover, sustainable library practices and the Open Science Initiative in Nigerian library schools will advance Diversity,

Figure 1: Open Science

Inclusion and green initiatives (Nnatu et al., 2024; David-West & Wali, 2024), as well as open research and education development (Sulyman et al., 2023; Yahaya, 2024).

Open Science (OS) and Sustainable LIS Research Practices

The use of open science in Library and Information Science (LIS) research practices facilitates the principles of transparency, collaboration, and accessibility throughout the entire research process. Its objective is to provide open access to research outputs, such as articles, data, and techniques, for broader distribution. This strategy is consistent with the objectives of LIS, which prioritise fair and equal access to information and effective management of knowledge. The concept of open science enhances sustainability by facilitating effective and transparent research procedures, diminishing obstacles to information exchange, and promoting collaboration across different disciplines. Foundational elements of open science encompass open access, transparency, and collaboration, which guarantee flexible, inclusive, and adaptable research methodologies to changing societal and technological demands.

The rapid growth of information resources and the need for equitable access to knowledge have emphasised the importance of open access in research and publication discourse. (Kamińska, Opaliński, & Wyciślik, 2022). The need for sustainability in research activities within the domain of Library and Information Science (LIS) is strongly congruent with the concepts of open access. Open access is crucial for ensuring LIS research is accessible and sustainable, fostering a cohesive, open, and inclusive research environment. (Arthur, Hearn, Ryan, Menon, & Khumalo, 2023).

Collaboration in Library and Information Science (LIS) research is vital for its long-term viability, as it facilitates knowledge exchange, data sharing, and methodologies among various fields and organizations, enhancing research through creative and inclusive ideas. (Kamińska, Opaliński, & Wyciślik, 2022). Furthermore, open science encourages collaboration beyond academics, including practitioners, policymakers, and the public, thereby amplifying the practical influence of LIS research (Thibault et al., 2023).

Transparency in open science refers to making the entire research process, including data, methodologies, and results, openly available and accessible (Sofi-Mahmudi et al., 2024). It is crucial in sustainable Library and Information Science (LIS) research for trust, reproducibility, and accountability for both theory, methodology and publication (Ngulube & Mosha, 2023; Ngulube & Ukwoma, 2021). By sharing data and methods, researchers ensure their findings can be verified and reproduced, ensuring credibility and sustainability (Grüning, 2023). And contributes to ethical information management, allowing stakeholders to understand data collection, processing, preservation, and serves as checks to data manipulation or selective reporting (Schöpfel & Azeroual, 2023; Sibinga, 2018). Research Data Management (RDM) and Sustainable LIS Research Practices

Research data management (RDM)

- Data sharing
- Data curation
- Ethical practices

Figure 2: Research Data Management

Effective research data management (RDM) in Library and Information Science (LIS), research practice is crucial for ensuring the sustainability and impact of research practices. Key components of RDM include data sharing, data curation, and ethical practices, each playing a vital role in enhancing the accessibility, usability, and integrity of research data.

Data sharing involves making research data accessible to other researchers, institutions, and the public (Abdullahi & Noorhidawati, 2020). In LIS, sharing data promotes transparency, allows for the verification and replication of studies, and fosters collaborative research (Alex-Nmecha & Onifade, 2023). And supports the principle of open science by liberalizing valuable data for broader use and analysis (Boué, Byrne, Hayes, Hoeng, & Peitsch, 2018), this enhances visibility and impact of LIS research and facilitates new discoveries and innovations.

Data curation refers to the process of managing and maintaining data throughout its lifecycle to ensure its long-term usability and integrity. In LIS, it involves organizing, preserving, and documenting data so that it remains accessible and useful over time through metadata creation, proper storage, and implementing data management plans (Tiwari, 2018).. The importance of data curation in research data management cannot be overstated, as it greatly influences the implementation of sustainable practices in the field of library and information science (LIS). This practice ensures the long-term use and conservation of research data, thereby creating an environment that encourages ethical and reusable data sharing. The principle of "anticipatory generification" (Parmiggiani & Amagyei, 2023) refers to the process of preserving previous datasets and adjusting them to anticipate future requirements, hence improving data reusability. The significance of its capacity for study replication, especially in domains such as visualisation, where specific questions require customised curation approaches, cannot be overstated (Garkov, Muller, Braun, Weiskopf, & Schreiber, 2022). The Data Curation Network serves as a prime example of sustainable collaboration among institutions, fostering ethical data governance and the exchange of resources (Carlson, Narlock, Blake, Herndon, & Imker, 2023). The importance of preserving research data is growing in the field of Library and Information Science (LIS), as a considerable proportion of academic departments acknowledge the necessity of implementing strong data management strategies (Maurya & Subaveerapandiyam, 2022).

Ethical practices in data management are essential for maintaining the integrity and trustworthiness of research practices. These practices guarantee the assurance of reliable and verifiable conclusions, promote transparency and accountability, and protect intellectual property rights. Pasupuleti (2024) asserts that upholding ethical standards such as honesty, responsibility, and regard for intellectual property is crucial for doing ethical research. These principles promote a cooperative atmosphere where data is regarded as a common resource. Adekugbe and Ibeh (2024) highlight the significance of interest groups and risk evaluations in the ethical management of data. Such structures are perceived to assist researchers in navigating the complexity of data sharing while protecting the rights of individuals and organisations. This necessitates the implementation of strong procedures for informed consent and privacy provisions.

According to the authors, the implementation "of legal and regulatory standards is" crucial for maintaining ethical data practices. They argue that such standards will enhance the development of strong systems for managing informed consent, privacy concerns, and regulatory compliance, hence reducing "the risks of data misuse or breaches." Furthermore, efficient data management is critical for ensuring the replication and verification of study results. Cunha-Oliveira, Ioannidis and Oliveira (2024) contend that meticulously well-structured and extensively recorded data are essential for researchers to reproduce investigations and authenticate findings. Effective data management procedures, including thorough documentation, meticulous data preservation, and well-defined organisational structures, empower researchers to validate results and expand upon previous research, thereby enhancing scientific advancement and upholding public confidence.

Librarians in Nigerian universities are becoming more involved in RDM, supporting research and scientific communication open access and transparency in research (Nwabugwu & Godwin, 2020). However, their participation is still limited due to challenges such as inadequate data management plans and insufficient funding (Adekoya et al., 2024). The adoption of open research practices, including open peer review and the use of institutional repositories, is growing among Nigerian librarians, improving their research profiles and visibility. Nevertheless, a lack of training and awareness hinders wider participation in these practices (Sulyman et al., 2023).

Data sharing among Library and Information Science (LIS) researchers is increasing, supported by social media and online platforms (Tella, 2023). Despite this progress, challenges such as inadequate policies and limited skills continue to impede effective data management, which is crucial for ensuring the usability of research data and aligning with the principles of open science (Borghini & Van Gulick, 2022).

Framework for Sustainable Library and Information Science Research and Practice

Differing ideologies, departmentalization, curricular outlook, duration of programme etc., among Nigeria library schools compared to the scenario in other countries calls for a paradigm shift. As a research-oriented discipline, establishing a structure for sustainable library and information science (LIS) research and practice using open science and research data management (RDM) at Nigerian library schools is crucial for multiple reasons. (see the next page)

Figure 3: Framework for Sustainable Library and Information Science Research and Practice

The Framework for Sustainable Library and Information Science (LIS) Research and Practice is a systematic methodology that directs the incorporation of sustainability principles into research and professional activities in the LIS discipline. It includes techniques, approaches, and operational standards intended to advance environmental, economic, and social

sustainability in library services, information management, and library and information science instruction. This framework provides a fundamental basis for improving research standards, promoting cooperation, guaranteeing the long-term availability of research data, and equipping students for the changing field of applied information science. Typically, such a framework would consist of the following components:

An integrated curriculum in LIS research practices combines diverse fields such as "information science, digital preservation, data science, and user experience," promoting multidisciplinary learning. It emphasizes theme, problem-oriented learning, interdisciplinary interaction, and practical application through practice-based research (Bakare & Bakare, 2024; Drake & Reid, 2018). The technique prepares learners to tackle new developments, such as artificial intelligence "in information systems, while integrating" theoretical knowledge and practical competencies in areas including digital curation, copyright legislation, and information management (Magoma, 2016). It facilitates comprehensive comprehension and flexibility in the changing information environment. Existing research deficiencies underscore the imperative for libraries to evolve and innovate, guaranteeing their relevance in a swiftly transforming technology environment (Khalid, Malik, & Mahmood, 2021).

Environmental sustainability includes green library techniques that include the use of energy-efficient technologies, green building standards such as "Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) certification (Waheed, 2019), and an emphasis on waste reduction through recycling and paper usage (Hauke, Charney, & Sahavirta, 2018). An effective web infrastructure encompasses energy-saving data centres and cloud storage systems to guarantee sustained access to digital resources (Dewitt, 2013).

Economic sustainability consists of funding, resource management, and value demonstration. To provide financial stability and optimize resources, libraries must pursue a variety of financing sources and allocate resources to cost-effective technologies (Ramachandran, 2024). Additionally, libraries must consistently evaluate and exhibit their impact while maintaining evidence-based practices to improve research visibility and impact (Thorpe & Howlett, 2020). Further, it must align their strategic plans with institutional and community requirements to ensure economic sustainability (Edwards, Gilroy, & Treadway, 2024).

Social sustainability, encompassing career growth and community engagement, provides inclusive research services to various groups and fosters collaborations with local organisations to improve outreach and service delivery (Mubofu & Mambo, 2021; Panda & Das, 2022). Furthermore, continuous training and knowledge sharing among library staff are essential for contemporary research on evolving practices and innovation (Owate, Iroeze, & Echem, 2020). Therefore, social sustainability as a crucial element in Nigerian Library and Information Science (LIS) research and practices influences community engagement, resources distribution, and the impact of initiatives. Libraries can function as centres for social entrepreneurship, boosting poverty reduction and sustainable development (Otike & Kiszl, 2024). Involving local communities in library activities promotes interest and engagement in sustainable practices.

Sustainable research and practice in Library and Information Science (LIS) are crucial for fostering innovation, knowledge production, and professional development. Key initiatives, such as integrating makerspaces, allow participants to become knowledge creators through experiential learning and collaboration, developing skills like leadership and teamwork, which are essential for advancing research (Edobor, 2022; Maceli, 2022). Sustainable innovation techniques, including business models that incorporate renewable resources, are necessary for

maintaining competitiveness in the field (Naveed, Zhuparova, Ahmad, & Fathollah Zadeh Aghdam, 2023; Rus, 2023). Libraries can also enhance continuous professional development by providing training that improves librarians' research capabilities (O'Toole, Sassen, Willis, Guerrero & Berg, 2023). Finally, adopting technology-driven sustainable practices ensures efficient, precise services that support research efforts (Ayinla & Aramide, 2022).

OUTCOME

The framework for sustainable Library and Information Science (LIS) research and practice through Open Science (OS) initiatives and Research Data Management (RDM) can produce numerous beneficial consequences for LIS institutions in Nigeria:

1. **Enhanced Curriculum:** The integration of OS and RDM into the LIS curriculum allows educational institutions to offer more contemporary, comprehensive courses in information management and open-access research, enhancing students' knowledge of data management, sharing, and reproducibility.
2. **Skill Acquisition:** The application of OS and RDM in educational initiatives ensures the acquisition of essential technical and methodological competencies, such as data curation, open-access publishing, and proficient digital tool usage, thereby equipping graduates with modern industry skills.
3. **Skilled workforce:** Learners who understand OS and RDM are better equipped to pursue careers as information professionals. Their ability to manage digital information and data increases their job prospects and significance in modern libraries, archives, and information centers.
4. **Quality Research:** Sustainable LIS research and practices, supported by OS and RDM initiatives, promote transparency, accountability, and accessibility in research, resulting in improved scholarly outputs. Libraries and information science schools that implement these methods stimulate their students, staff, and faculty to participate in more complex and relevant research endeavours, thus enhancing the institution's scientific quality.
5. **Increased Research Visibility:** Open science approaches facilitate the dissemination of research products outside conventional paywalls. Consequently, research from LIS schools becomes more globally accessible, enhancing citations and academic influence. RDM ensures effective data and results management, facilitates reuse, and enhances visibility and accessibility.
6. **Collaboration:** Open Science encourages research collaboration among institutions and fields globally, fostering a more creative and integrated academic environment. This encourages LIS schools to collaborate with scholars and organizations to enhance their research and practice.

These outcomes are anticipated to enhance the development and significance of LIS education and practice, ensuring that Nigerian LIS institutions stay relevant and aligned to global best practices.

Steps towards Sustainable Library and Information Science Research and Practice in Nigerian Library Schools

To achieve sustainable Library and Information Science (LIS) research and practice in Nigerian library schools, several strategic steps must be undertaken. These steps aptly encapsulate the dynamic and proactive engagement required to advance sustainable Library and Information Science (LIS) research and practice in Nigerian library schools through the adoption of Open Science and Research Data Management (RDM). These include:

1. Continuous Monitoring and Adaptation this include Sustainable Practices such as constantly monitoring and updating practices to ensure they are sustainable. This involves regular assessment of resource usage, environmental impact, and long-term viability of LIS practices. And adoption of open science which represents a shift towards more transparent, accessible, and collaborative research. By staying attuned to the latest Open Science initiatives, Nigerian library schools can ensure their research remains relevant, widely disseminated, and impactful.
2. Integration of Innovative Practices which encompasses Research Data Management (RDM) and curricular relevance. Effective RDM is essential for the sustainable research practices, professional currency and best practices in data management, ensuring data integrity, accessibility, and reproducibility in one hand. While curricular relevance entails continuously revision and update of the curricula to incorporate the latest advancements in open Science and RDM.
3. Responding to challenges and opportunities such as identification of barriers and staying updated with the latest developments which allows LIS schools to quickly identify and respond to barriers in implementing sustainable practices. Furthermore, opportunities can be leveraged to keep abreast of global trends and advancements in Open Science and RDM by LIS schools and professionals for collaboration, funding, and development.
4. Empirical Assessment and Feedback Loops which include data-driven decisions and Continuous Improvement for regular checks and assessments, sustainable LIS research and practice require ongoing empirical evaluation. Regular assessment of the impact of Open Science and RDM practices in LIS educators and administrators can refine their approaches, ensuring sustained progress and adaptation to new challenges.
5. Building a sustainable future through long-term vision and community collaboration, sustainable LIS research and practice entails building a foundation for the future. This implies a forward-looking approach, where Nigerian library schools not only respond to current trends but also anticipate future needs and developments. Open science fosters a collaborative research environment. By staying connected with the global LIS community, Nigerian library schools can contribute to and benefit from collective efforts towards sustainability.
6. Creating synergy for a unified LIS field through departalisation, faculty location and curriculum harmonization. Location of LIS schools in the faculty of education has further reduced the field's relevance and impact as a field of knowledge compared to its contemporaries in other countries. Hence, the current move to creates the faculty of LIS, and or relocation to other related faculties has proved a challenge to the unity that exists in the field in Nigeria., The current challenge calls for synergy among the library schools, and professionals in the field.

The adoption of open science and RDM in the frameworks of Nigerian library schools ensure innovation, and effective preparation of their students for the challenges of modern librarianship and contribution to global LIS community.

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that sustainable library and information science research and practice through open science and research data management is a vital aspect of librarianship in the contemporary digital age. Furthermore, Nigerian library schools have trailed behind due to their incapacity to embrace the transformations and rise to the challenges of research innovation through open science and research data management initiatives. In Nigerian library schools, the practice of open science and research data management is still in its infancy. It identified inadequate skills, technological decay, poor funding, and other challenges to sustainable library and information science research and practice. It further concluded that a change of paradigm in research practices through framework development is a fundamental step for quality research practice among the library schools in Nigerian Library Schools

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study recommends that Nigerian library schools should:

1. Integrate open science and research data management into LIS curricula and research activities.
2. Implement continuous capacity-building initiatives for faculty and students.
3. Invest in modern digital infrastructure to support adoption and implementation.
4. Strengthen partnerships with international institutions and professional organizations for knowledge transfer.

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